

SMS Spam Detection Using Machine Learning Classifiers: A Comparative Study of Model Performance

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Abstract

SMS spam is becoming an increasing issue in internet communication, threatening the privacy of users and network security. This paper is a comparative analysis of some machine learning spammers for SMS spam filtering from the SMS Spam Collection corpus. The 5,574 manually labeled messages (86.5% ham and 13.5% spam) were preprocessed from tokenization, removal of stop-words, stemming, and TF-IDF vectorization. Five machine learning algorithms— Naïve Bayes, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest, and Voting Classifier— were trained and tested on accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score scores. Among them, the SVM algorithm was best overall with 98.1% accuracy, 0.97 precision, 0.89 recall, and an F1-score of 0.93 with improved ability to distinguish between spam and legitimate messages. The study confirms that proper preprocessing and feature extraction greatly enhance the performance of SMS spam detection. The introduced SVM-based method is practically applicable in real-world systems to enhance message filtering effectiveness and decrease user exposure to spam.

Keywords: *SMS Spam Detection, Machine Learning, Vector Machine, Random Forest, TF-IDF.*